

Disease Subtyping for Computational Pathology Benchmarking with TCGA dataset — White Paper

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Abstract

Advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and large language models (LLMs) are transforming computational pathology, yet the field still lacks robust public benchmarkings for disease subtyping. The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) offers a rich repository of whole slide images (WSIs) and associated data for various types of human cancers; however, its primary diagnostic labels may pose challenges for AI models due to inconsistencies, overlapping categories, and high interobserver variability, limiting its effectiveness for robust model validation.

This white paper addresses these limitations by proposing a rational and standardized classification framework for disease subtypes within the TCGA dataset, specifically designed for benchmarking pathology AI models and LLMs. We introduce two distinct classification schemes: one optimized for WSI classification and another for pathology report classification, acknowledging that morphologically similar findings may carry different nomenclature based on context. Our framework systematically re-evaluates the TCGA primary diagnoses across various organ systems, merging ambiguous or outdated categories and excluding rare entities. This refined approach aims to provide a more consistent and AI-ready dataset, thereby facilitating more accurate and reproducible benchmarking of foundation models and LLMs in computational pathology.

1. Introduction

The advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) and image analysis technologies continues to significantly impact pathology research and practice. Numerous AI models targeting whole slide images (WSIs) have been developed, with a recent proliferation of general-purpose foundation models¹⁻⁵ serving as backbones for various applications. These models show promise in addressing inherent challenges in computational pathology, such as limited annotated data and inter-institutional variability.

Foundation models are typically benchmarked across multiple downstream tasks⁶. In pathology, these large pre-trained models are trained on massive, diverse datasets that commonly include disease classification, subtyping, biomarker prediction, segmentation, as well as image search and retrieval. The dataset used for validation is extremely important⁷, but there are only a few that are publicly available. The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) project⁸ (<https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>) stands as one of the largest WSI datasets of human cancers, recognized for its diversity spanning multiple institutions, staining protocols, scanner types, and organ systems, making it the most established dataset in the field.

While TCGA provides standardized primary pathology diagnoses, these were not originally intended for AI labeling purposes, which presents significant challenges when used for disease subtyping. The existing primary diagnoses are not always mutually exclusive, with some disease concepts encompassing others. For example, "adenocarcinoma, NOS" in pancreas encompasses the other category "infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS".

Additionally, pathology diagnosis is not completely standardized; inter-observer variation is evident in some domain⁹⁻¹¹, the terminology may be varied between the different institutions¹² (e.g. "high-grade dysplasia" vs "severe dysplasia"). Furthermore, some disease nomenclature is outdated or uncommon in current practice. As a result, despite the TCGA dataset containing numerous organs involved with various cancers, their utility for AI validation have often been limited to specific organs such as the lung and kidney.

Concurrently, advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) have enabled the analysis of non-image data such as text and tabular data^{13,14}. Kefeli et al. extracted and curated pathology report text from TCGA—originally stored in PDF format—and made it publicly available¹⁵. Pathology reports often contain free-text narratives, inconsistent formatting, and a combination of structured and unstructured elements¹⁶, which previously posed significant challenges for standardization and systematic analysis.

This white paper proposes a rational classification of disease subtypes based on TCGA primary diagnoses, designed specifically for benchmarking pathology AI models and LLMs. We present two classification schemes: one for WSI classification and another for pathology report classification. These two schemes acknowledge that morphologically indistinguishable findings may carry different nomenclature based on anatomical site or clinical context. Our framework includes only disease categories with at least three available cases containing diagnostic slides, excluding rarer entities. We excluded lymph nodes and bone marrow because immunohistochemistry is important for the diagnosis and classification of hematolymphoid tumors. We also excluded bone and the nervous system since the number of available WSIs in the TCGA atlas is limited.

2. Modified Classification

2.1 Adrenal Glands

"Paranglioma" and "extra-adrenal paranglioma" are merged since they represent the same entity. Paranglioma and pheochromocytoma are generally considered malignant¹⁷. The distinction between pheochromocytoma and paranglioma is based on the primary tumor location, meaning that pathology images alone may not determine the diagnosis. (Table 1)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
ACC	Adrenal cortical carcinoma	227	Adrenal cortical carcinoma	Adrenal cortical carcinoma
PCPG	Pheochromocytoma, NOS	117	Pheochromocytoma	Paraganglioma
PCPG	Pheochromocytoma, malignant	47	Pheochromocytoma	Paraganglioma
PCPG	Extra-adrenal paraganglioma, NOS	18	Paraganglioma	Paraganglioma
PCPG	Extra-adrenal paraganglioma, malignant	6	Paraganglioma	Paraganglioma
PCPG	Paraganglioma, NOS	4	Paraganglioma	Paraganglioma
PCPG	Paraganglioma, malignant	4	Paraganglioma	Paraganglioma

Table 1. Modified classification of the adrenal glands

2.2 Urinary Bladder

Most cases are transitional cell carcinoma (urothelial carcinoma in current terminology), except for one case each of pure squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma. This categorization should *not* be used for AI classification. (Table 2)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
BLCA	Transitional cell carcinoma	388	-	-
BLCA	Papillary transitional cell carcinoma	66	-	-
BLCA	Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
BLCA	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
BLCA	Carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-

Table 2: Modified classification of the urinary bladder. The symbol '-' denotes classes should be excluded from the classification.

2.3 Brain

The current WHO classification¹⁸ incorporates molecular features, which introduces discrepancies when compared to TCGA diagnoses that rely solely on morphological characteristics. Nevertheless, the TCGA-based classification remains valid for the purposes of AI benchmarking. (Table 3)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
GBM	Glioblastoma	860	Glioblastoma	Glioblastoma
LGG	Mixed glioma	216	Mixed glioma	Mixed glioma
LGG	Oligodendroglioma, NOS	204	Oligodendroglioma	Oligodendroglioma
LGG	Astrocytoma, anaplastic	164	Anaplastic astrocytoma	Anaplastic astrocytoma
LGG	Oligodendroglioma, anaplastic	155	Anaplastic oligodendroglioma	Anaplastic oligodendroglioma
LGG	Astrocytoma, NOS	104	Astrocytoma	Astrocytoma
LGG	--	1	-	-

Table 3: Modified classification of the brain. The symbol '-' denotes classes should be excluded from the classification.

2.4 Breast

Infiltrating (invasive) ductal carcinoma is largely synonymous with "invasive breast carcinoma, no special type" in the current WHO classification¹⁹. The original terminology has been retained in the report classification, anticipating that Large Language Models (LLMs) may reference both the original reports and the disease list provided here. The categories "Infiltrating duct mixed with other types of carcinoma" and "Infiltrating lobular mixed with other types of carcinoma" should be excluded, as the breakdown of "other types of carcinomas" is not available. "Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma" contains both "ductal carcinoma" and "lobular carcinoma" components; developers may consider multi-labeling for this category depending on their specific purpose. Medullary carcinoma and pleomorphic carcinoma are currently classified under the broader category of "invasive breast carcinoma of NST"¹⁹; however, they remain as distinct subcategories here due to their recognizable morphology. All cases labeled as "intraductal papillary adenocarcinoma with invasion" are invasive breast carcinomas with papillary morphology. (Table 4)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
BRCA	Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS	805	Invasive ductal carcinoma	Invasive carcinoma of no special type
BRCA	Lobular carcinoma, NOS	204	Invasive lobular carcinoma	Invasive lobular carcinoma
BRCA	Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma	27	Ductal and lobular carcinoma	Ductal and lobular carcinoma
BRCA	Infiltrating duct mixed with other types of carcinoma	20	-	-
BRCA	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	20	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	Mucinous adenocarcinoma
BRCA	Metaplastic carcinoma, NOS	13	Metaplastic carcinoma	Metaplastic carcinoma
BRCA	Intraductal papillary adenocarcinoma with invasion	7	Invasive ductal carcinoma	Invasive carcinoma of no special type
BRCA	Medullary carcinoma, NOS	7	Medullary carcinoma	Medullary carcinoma
BRCA	Infiltrating lobular mixed with other types of carcinoma	7	-	-
BRCA	Invasive micropapillary carcinoma	4	Invasive micropapillary carcinoma	Invasive micropapillary carcinoma
BRCA	Pleomorphic carcinoma	3	Pleomorphic carcinoma	Pleomorphic carcinoma
BRCA	Paget disease and infiltrating duct carcinoma of breast	3	Invasive ductal carcinoma	Paget disease of the breast
BRCA	Papillary carcinoma, NOS	2	-	-
BRCA	Phyllodes tumor, malignant	2	-	-
BRCA	Tubular adenocarcinoma	2	-	-
BRCA	Carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
BRCA	Secretory carcinoma of breast	1	-	-
BRCA	Apocrine adenocarcinoma	1	-	-
BRCA	Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma	1	-	-
BRCA	Cribriform carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
BRCA	Adenoid cystic carcinoma	1	-	-
BRCA	Basal cell carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-

Table 4. Modified classification of the breast. "-" denotes exclusion.

2.5 Uterine cervix

All squamous cell carcinomas are merged since a diagnosis incorporating the keratinizing pattern is often difficult to reproduce. (Table 5)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
CEC	Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	163	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
CEC	Squamous cell carcinoma, large cell, nonkeratinizing, NOS	36	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
CEC	Squamous cell carcinoma, keratinizing, NOS	27	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
CEC	Adenocarcinoma, endocervical type	18	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
CEC	Mucinous adenocarcinoma, endocervical type	17	Adenocarcinoma	Mucinous adenocarcinoma
CEC	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	7	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
CEC	Adenosquamous carcinoma	6	Adenosquamous carcinoma	Adenosquamous carcinoma
CEC	Endometrioid adenocarcinoma, NOS	3	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
CEC	Basaloid squamous cell carcinoma	1	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
CEC	Papillary squamous cell carcinoma	1	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma

Table 5: Modified classification of the uterine cervix. “-” represents the exclusion.

2.6 Colon and Rectum

Colon and rectum share histological structures and accordingly should be treated as a single entity. Considering the frequency of minor subtypes, a two-tier classification is appropriate. (Table 6)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
COAD	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	389	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Adenocarcinoma, NOS
COAD	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	63	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	Mucinous adenocarcinoma
COAD	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	2	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Adenocarcinoma, NOS
COAD	--	1	-	-
COAD	Adenosquamous carcinoma	1	-	-
COAD	Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation	1	-	-
COAD	Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes	1	-	-
COAD	Carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
READ	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	134	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Adenocarcinoma, NOS
READ	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	15	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	Mucinous adenocarcinoma
READ	Adenocarcinoma in tubulovillous adenoma	8	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Adenocarcinoma, NOS
READ	Tubular adenocarcinoma	5	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Adenocarcinoma, NOS

READ	Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes	2	-	-
READ	--	1	-	-

Table 6: Modified classification of the colon and rectum. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.7 Esophagus

The identification of keratinizing patterns remains challenging due to their inherent ambiguity and poor reproducibility. Therefore, a simplified classification is considered more robust. (Table 7)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
ESCA	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	86	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
ESCA	Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	65	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
ESCA	Squamous cell carcinoma, keratinizing, NOS	5	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
ESCA	Basaloid squamous cell carcinoma	1	Squamous cell carcinoma	Squamous cell carcinoma
ESCA	Tubular adenocarcinoma	1	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma

Table 7: Modified classification of the esophagus

2.8 Eye (Uveal Melanoma)

All subcategories belong to the broader category of malignant melanoma. This subclassification is not suitable for AI benchmarking. (Table 8)

Project	Original Classification	N	Report classification	Image classification
UVM	Mixed epithelioid and spindle cell melanoma	39	-	-
UVM	Spindle cell melanoma, NOS	19	-	-
UVM	Epithelioid cell melanoma	12	-	-
UVM	Spindle cell melanoma, type B	9	-	-
UVM	Malignant melanoma, NOS	1	-	-

Table 8: Modified classification of the eye. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.9 Head and Neck

The identification of keratinizing patterns remains challenging due to their inherent ambiguity and poor reproducibility. This subclassification is not suitable for AI classification. (Table 9)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
HNSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	400	-	-
HNSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, keratinizing, NOS	56	-	-
HNSC	Basaloid squamous cell carcinoma	9	-	-
HNSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, large cell, nonkeratinizing, NOS	6	-	-
HNSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, spindle cell	1	-	-

Table 9. Modified classification of the head and neck. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.10 Kidney

There are three independent TCGA projects related to kidney. The classifications provided by TCGA are suitable for use in AI. The nomenclature has been updated to align with the current WHO classification. (Table 10)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
KIRC	Clear cell adenocarcinoma, NOS	506	Clear cell renal cell carcinoma	Clear cell renal cell carcinoma
KIRP	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	300	Papillary renal cell carcinoma	Papillary renal cell carcinoma
KICH	Renal cell carcinoma, chromophobe type	121	Chromophobe renal cell carcinoma	Chromophobe renal cell carcinoma
KIRC	Renal cell carcinoma, NOS	13	-	-

Table 10. Modified classification of the kidney. The symbol '-' denotes exclusion.

2.11 Lining of the chest or abdomen (Mesothelioma)

The category "mesothelioma, malignant" was excluded since it may be epithelioid or biphasic. (Table 11)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
MESO	Epithelioid mesothelioma, malignant	62	Epithelioid mesothelioma	Epithelioid mesothelioma
MESO	Mesothelioma, biphasic, malignant	19	Biphasic mesothelioma	Biphasic mesothelioma
MESO	Mesothelioma, malignant	5	-	-
MESO	Fibrous mesothelioma, malignant	1	-	-

Table 11. Modified classification of the lining of the chest or abdomen. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.12 Liver

All hepatocellular carcinoma subtypes are merged into one category because of the low reproducibility. (Table 12)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
LIHC	Hepatocellular carcinoma, NOS	364	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Hepatocellular carcinoma
LIHC	Combined hepatocellular carcinoma and cholangiocarcinoma	6	Combined hepatocellular-cholangiocarcinoma	Combined hepatocellular-cholangiocarcinoma
LIHC	Hepatocellular carcinoma, clear cell type	4	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Hepatocellular carcinoma
LIHC	Hepatocellular carcinoma, fibrolamellar	3	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Hepatocellular carcinoma
LIHC	Hepatocellular carcinoma, spindle cell variant	1	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Hepatocellular carcinoma
LIHC	Clear cell adenocarcinoma, NOS	1	Hepatocellular carcinoma	Hepatocellular carcinoma

CHOL	Cholangiocarcinoma	39	Cholangiocarcinoma	Cholangiocarcinoma
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Table 12. Modified classification of the liver. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.13 Lung

There are two independent TCGA projects for lung. Due to lower interobserver agreement between different adenocarcinoma subtypes, classification based on the two projects (LUAD and LUSC) is more realistic. (Table 13)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
LUSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	479	LUSC	LUSC
LUAD	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	334	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes	104	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	29	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Acinar cell carcinoma	19	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Bronchiolo-alveolar carcinoma, non-mucinous	16	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	16	LUAD	LUAD
LUSC	Basaloid squamous cell carcinoma	13	LUSC	LUSC
LUSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, keratinizing, NOS	13	LUSC	LUSC
LUAD	Solid carcinoma, NOS	6	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Bronchio-alveolar carcinoma, mucinous	5	LUAD	LUAD
LUSC	Papillary squamous cell carcinoma	4	LUSC	LUSC
LUSC	Squamous cell carcinoma, large cell, nonkeratinizing, NOS	3	LUSC	LUSC
LUAD	Micropapillary carcinoma, NOS	3	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Bronchiolo-alveolar adenocarcinoma, NOS	3	LUAD	LUAD
LUAD	Signet ring cell carcinoma	1	LUAD	LUAD

Table 13. Modified classification of the lung

2.14 Ovary

All of the categories are currently recognized as serous carcinoma. This categorization should *not* be used for AI classification. (Table 14)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
OV	Serous cystadenocarcinoma, NOS	102	-	-
OV	Papillary serous cystadenocarcinoma	4	-	-
OV	Cystadenocarcinoma, NOS	1	-	-

Table 14. Modified classification of the ovary

2.15 Pancreas

Cases labeled as "mucinous adenocarcinoma" are mucin-producing adenocarcinomas rather than so-called colloid carcinomas, meaning their distinction from ductal carcinoma is potentially ambiguous. Typically, mucinous carcinoma emphasizes intracellular and extracellular mucin production by tumor cells, whereas colloid carcinoma emphasizes large extracellular pools of mucin with floating clusters of tumor cells. Classification between adenocarcinoma and neuroendocrine carcinoma is more appropriate. (Table 15)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
PAAD	Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS	176	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
PAAD	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	18	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
PAAD	Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS	8	Neuroendocrine carcinoma	Neuroendocrine carcinoma
PAAD	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	5	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
PAAD	Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS	1	-	-
PAAD	Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes	1	-	-

Table 15. Modified classification of the pancreas. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.16 Prostate

The diagnostic criteria of infiltrating duct carcinoma (ductal adenocarcinoma of the prostate) are insufficiently defined, and often admixed with more common “adenocarcinoma, NOS” (acinar adenocarcinoma). The current subtyping of prostate carcinoma in the TCGA dataset is accordingly inappropriate. (Table 16)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
PRAD	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	445	-	-
PRAD	Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS	4	-	-

Table 16. Modified classification of the prostate. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.17 Skin (Melanoma)

All cases are melanoma but labeled using a different classification; some are based on growth pattern, others on cell morphology. The skin dataset should thus not be used for AI classification. (Table 17)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
SKCM	Malignant melanoma, NOS	424	-	-
SKCM	Nodular melanoma	22	-	-
SKCM	Epithelioid cell melanoma	7	-	-
SKCM	Amelanotic melanoma	7	-	-
SKCM	Superficial spreading melanoma	5	-	-
SKCM	Spindle cell melanoma, NOS	3	-	-
SKCM	Acral lentiginous melanoma, malignant	3	-	-
SKCM	Lentigo maligna melanoma	2	-	-
SKCM	Mixed epithelioid and spindle cell melanoma	1	-	-
SKCM	Desmoplastic melanoma, malignant	1	-	-

Table 17. Modified classification of the skin (melanoma). “-” denotes the exclusion

2.18 Soft tissue

Undifferentiated sarcoma and malignant fibrous histiocytoma (MFH) are merged since the distinction is morphologically ambiguous and they are currently recognized as the same disease entity: undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma. The entity MFH no longer exists using current terminology. Both nomenclatures are kept since they are reported in different ways. The category myxofibrosarcoma (more commonly used than

"fibromyxosarcoma") remains due to its distinct morphological characteristics. Myxofibrosarcoma is often used interchangeably with "myxoid malignant fibrous histiocytoma" in reports. Synovial sarcoma has been grouped into one entity. (Table 18)

Project	Original Classification	N	Report classification	Image classification
SARC	Leiomyosarcoma, NOS	152	Leiomyosarcoma	Leiomyosarcoma
SARC	Fibromyxosarcoma	141	Myxofibrosarcoma (Myxoid malignant fibrous histiocytoma)	Myxofibrosarcoma
SARC	Undifferentiated sarcoma	107	Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma (Malignant fibrous histiocytoma)	Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma
SARC	Dedifferentiated liposarcoma	87	Dedifferentiated liposarcoma	Dedifferentiated liposarcoma
SARC	Malignant fibrous histiocytoma	54	Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma (Malignant fibrous histiocytoma)	Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma
SARC	Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor	27	Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor	Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor
SARC	Synovial sarcoma, spindle cell	12	Synovial sarcoma	Synovial sarcoma
SARC	Synovial sarcoma, biphasic	6	Synovial sarcoma	Synovial sarcoma
SARC	Giant cell sarcoma	4	-	-
SARC	Myxoid leiomyosarcoma	3	Leiomyosarcoma	Leiomyosarcoma
SARC	Synovial sarcoma, NOS	2	Synovial sarcoma	Synovial sarcoma
SARC	Pleomorphic liposarcoma	2	-	-
SARC	Liposarcoma, well differentiated	1	-	-
SARC	Abdominal fibromatosis	1	-	-
SARC	Aggressive fibromatosis	1	-	-

Table 18. Modified classification of the soft tissue (sarcoma). "-" denotes the exclusion.

2.19 Stomach

The original classification scheme was inconsistent because some criteria were based on differentiation, while others were based on morphological architecture. (Table 19)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
STAD	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	153	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
STAD	Adenocarcinoma, intestinal type	85	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
STAD	Tubular adenocarcinoma	84	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
STAD	Carcinoma, diffuse type	72	Poorly cohesive carcinoma	Poorly cohesive carcinoma
STAD	Mucinous adenocarcinoma	23	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
STAD	Signet ring cell carcinoma	14	Poorly cohesive carcinoma	Poorly cohesive carcinoma
STAD	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	9	Adenocarcinoma	Adenocarcinoma
STAD	Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes	2	-	-

Table 19. Modified classification of the stomach. "-" denotes the exclusion.

2.20 Testis

The original classification can be used for AI classification as well. The subtyping is appropriate for AI classification. (Table 20)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
TGCT	Seminoma	94	Seminoma	Seminoma
TGCT	Mixed germ cell tumor	50	Mixed germ cell tumor	Mixed germ cell tumor
TGCT	--	43	-	-
TGCT	Embryonal carcinoma, NOS	42	Embryonal carcinoma	Embryonal carcinoma
TGCT	Yolk sac tumor	6	Yolk sac tumor	Yolk sac tumor
TGCT	Teratoma, benign	4	Teratoma	Teratoma
TGCT	Teratocarcinoma	2	-	-

Table 20. Modified classification of the testis. "--" denotes the exclusion.

2.21 Thymus

All thymomas are considered potentially malignant²⁰. (Table 21)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
THYM	Thymoma, type A, malignant	25	Thymoma, type A	Thymoma, type A
THYM	Thymoma, type A, NOS	2	Thymoma, type A	Thymoma, type A
THYM	Thymoma, type AB, malignant	39	Thymoma, type AB	Thymoma, type AB
THYM	Thymoma, type AB, NOS	7	Thymoma, type AB	Thymoma, type AB
THYM	Thymoma, type B1, malignant	35	Thymoma, type B1	Thymoma, type B1
THYM	Thymoma, type B1, NOS	1	Thymoma, type B1	Thymoma, type B1
THYM	Thymoma, type B2, malignant	43	Thymoma, type B2	Thymoma, type B2
THYM	Thymoma, type B2, NOS	5	Thymoma, type B2	Thymoma, type B2
THYM	Thymoma, type B3, malignant	24	Thymoma, type B3	Thymoma, type B3
THYM	Thymic carcinoma, NOS	11	Thymic carcinoma	Thymic carcinoma

Table 21. Modified classification of the thymus. "--" denotes the exclusion.

2.22 Thyroid

The term "papillary carcinoma, diffuse sclerosing variant" is more commonly used than "nonencapsulated sclerosing carcinoma." (Table 22)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
THCA	Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS	365	Papillary carcinoma	Papillary thyroid carcinoma, NOS
THCA	Papillary carcinoma, follicular variant	107	Follicular variant of Papillary carcinoma	Papillary thyroid carcinoma, follicular variant
THCA	Papillary carcinoma, columnar cell	38	Papillary carcinoma, columnar cell variant	Papillary thyroid carcinoma, columnar cell variant
THCA	Nonencapsulated sclerosing carcinoma	5	Papillary carcinoma, diffuse sclerosing variant	Papillary thyroid carcinoma, diffuse sclerosing variant
THCA	Follicular adenocarcinoma, NOS	1	-	-

THCA	Follicular carcinoma, minimally invasive	1	-	-
THCA	Oxyphilic adenocarcinoma	1	-	-
THCA	Carcinoma, NOS	1	-	-

Table 22. Modified classification of the thyroid. “-” denotes the exclusion.

2.23 Uterine corpus

Malignant Mixed Müllerian tumor (MMMT) is a synonym for carcinosarcoma. Several subtypes of serous carcinoma and endometrioid carcinoma have been merged. (Table 23)

Project	Original Classification	n	Report classification	Image classification
UCEC	Endometrioid adenocarcinoma, NOS	416	Endometrioid carcinoma	Endometrioid carcinoma
UCEC	Serous cystadenocarcinoma, NOS	134	Serous carcinoma	Serous carcinoma
UCS	Mullerian mixed tumor	71	Carcinosarcoma (Malignant mixed mullerian tumors)	Carcinosarcoma
UCS	Carcinosarcoma	19	Carcinosarcoma (Malignant mixed mullerian tumors)	Carcinosarcoma
UCEC	Serous surface papillary carcinoma	6	Serous carcinoma	Serous carcinoma
UCEC	Papillary serous cystadenocarcinoma	4	Serous carcinoma	Serous carcinoma
UCEC	Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS	2	-	-
UCEC	Endometrioid adenocarcinoma, secretory variant	2	Endometrioid adenocarcinoma	Endometrioid adenocarcinoma
UCEC	Clear cell adenocarcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
UCEC	Adenocarcinoma, NOS	1	-	-
UCS	Mesodermal mixed tumor	1	-	-

Table 23. Modified classification of the terine corpus. “-” denotes the exclusion.

3. Discussion

The proposed classification framework represents an important effort to better leverage the extensive resources of TCGA for computational pathology. Our approach directly addresses critical challenges inherent in using historical pathological data for modern AI applications, particularly those related to inconsistencies stemming from evolving diagnostic criteria and the need for highly structured, standardized labels for AI training.

Developing robust AI models in pathology requires addressing nomenclature inconsistencies that undermine generalizability and reliability. Variability in diagnostic terminology across institutions introduces semantic drift, where learned representations fail to transfer effectively. This challenge is particularly pronounced in multimodal models that integrate WSIs with textual data, as ambiguity in pathology reports disrupts alignment between image features and clinical descriptors. The absence of global benchmarks for nomenclature-driven tasks further

complicates evaluation, while inconsistent terminology poses obstacles for regulatory compliance and external validation. Ethical concerns also arise when ambiguous nomenclature leads to misclassification, potentially affecting patient safety and liability.

A critical step toward mitigating these risks is the establishment of classification schemes that are both mutually exclusive and exhibit low interobserver variability. Lack of mutual exclusivity introduces ambiguity during training and validation, degrading model performance. Although complete elimination of interobserver variability is challenging in pathology, rational restructuring of diagnostic categories can substantially reduce this issue. For example, in the uterine cervix, original TCGA classifications include ‘Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS,’ ‘Squamous cell carcinoma, large cell, nonkeratinizing,’ and ‘Squamous cell carcinoma, keratinizing.’ These distinctions are often subjective and prone to interpretation, making them less suitable for AI training. Consolidating such subtypes into a single, broader ‘Squamous cell carcinoma’ category provides a clearer, mutually exclusive target, thereby improving reproducibility, reducing semantic ambiguity, and enhancing model generalizability.

Note: As datasets age, they run the risk of no longer being contemporary. This is because the nomenclature and classifications of tumors change, especially given the rapid advancement of molecular findings in these neoplasms.

To achieve these principles across different data modalities, our framework introduces two complementary classification schemes for image and report analysis. This distinction is important because the information discernible from a WSI often differs fundamentally from the **broader clinical context** provided in a pathology report, necessitating different approaches to ensure mutual exclusivity and reduced variability for each. For example, a "pheochromocytoma" and a "paraganglioma" are distinct entities in a clinical report, primarily differentiated by their anatomical location (adrenal gland vs. extra-adrenal)¹⁷. However, morphologically, these tumors can be indistinguishable on a WSI. Our image classification scheme therefore groups them under a shared "Paraganglioma" category, reflecting their common visual characteristics and ensuring a mutually exclusive visual class, while the report classification maintains their anatomical distinction.

Our framework also addresses the problem of interobserver variability and outdated nomenclature in pathology. By systematically merging categories where morphological distinctions are ambiguous or poorly reproducible, we create more robust and reliable ground truth labels. This standardization is vital for training AI models that can support high consistency and accuracy, mirroring the goal of reducing diagnostic discrepancies among human pathologists.

The establishment of this standardized classification framework is important for fair and reproducible benchmarking of AI models. In a rapidly evolving field, the ability for different research groups to train and evaluate their AI models against a common, curated ground truth is valuable for meaningful progress. Without such a standard, comparing model performance across studies becomes challenging, hindering the identification of more effective approaches. By providing clean, AI-ready labels, our framework significantly reduces the substantial effort researchers typically spend on data curation and label reconciliation, allowing them to focus on developing novel model architectures and training methodologies – particularly in scenarios where pathologist input is limited.

While our classification rationalizes TCGA data for AI, it is important to acknowledge the inherent limitations of retrospective data. The original TCGA dataset was collected over a decade ago, and certain molecular or immunohistochemical markers, which are now standard for definitive diagnosis and subtyping in many cancers, might not have been consistently available or recorded. This can limit the granularity of some classifications, as our framework is constrained by the information present in the original TCGA diagnoses. The justified exclusion of rare entities (those with fewer than three cases) ensures robust AI training but means that models trained solely on this framework might not perform optimally on extremely rare disease subtypes, suggesting future work could explore **few-shot** or **transfer learning** approaches for these cases. Ultimately, by making this re-classified dataset publicly available (<https://github.com/XXXXXX/>), we aim to provide a valuable resource for developing AI tools that can assist pathologists, accelerate drug discovery, and potentially improve patient outcomes, thereby contributing to the clinical relevance and translational impact of AI in pathology.

4. Data Availability

The complete set of proposed classifications is detailed within the manuscript. For ease of access, these classifications have also been made available in CSV format at <https://github.com/XXXXXX/>.

5. Code Availability

Not applicable

6. Reference

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Author Contributions

WU and HRT conceptualized the project. WU prepared the initial classification scheme, which was subsequently edited in collaboration with RWK. LP and JJG reviewed all classifications. The manuscript was drafted by WU and further edited by LP and HRT. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Competing Interests

NO